

TWO NEW SPECIES OF CLEOMENINI (COLEOPTERA: CERAMBYCIDAE) FROM MYANMAR AND THAILAND

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ABSTRACT: *Cleomenes putaoensis* sp. nov. from Myanmar (50 km E Putao) and *Dere tatianae* sp. nov. from NW Thailand (Mae Hong Son province) are described. The distinguishing characters are discussed.

KEY WORDS: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, new species, taxonomy, Myanmar, Thailand

The genus *Cleomenes* Thomson, 1864 includes about 40 species from the South-East of Palaearctic Region and from Oriental Region; but only one species *C. chryseus* Gahan, 1906 is known from Myanmar. The genus *Dere* White, 1855 includes about 50 species distributed from Africa along south Asia to Japan and Oriental Region. Three species are known from Thailand: *D. adelpha* Holzschuh, 1995, *D. minima* Holzschuh, 2015 and *D. punctifrons* Holzschuh, 1991.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1 – 30.5 mm 1:2.8 – 4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustration were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cleomenes putaoensis sp. nov.

(Fig. 1)

Type locality. Myanmar (N Burma), 50 km E Putao, environs Nan Thi village, 950 m.

Description. A single female available; elytral design is similar to *C. lautus* Holzschuh, 1991, but body long and narrow, black; palpi, antennae and legs orange-yellow; antennae with 4 black apical joints; internal surfaces of hind femora slightly darkened.

Head goldish pubescence nearly indistinct, eyes very big, strongly convex; genae very narrow, about as wide as 3rd antennal joint; antennal tubercle angulated, separated by about width width of 1st antennal joint.

Antennae strongly thickened apically, not reaching elytral apices; 1st antennal joint about 2.5 times shorter than 3rd; 3rd elytral joint reaching elytra; apical angles of 3rd - 10th joints sharp, more attenuated distally.

Prothorax about 1.4 times longer than basal width; slightly widened behind middle; with anterior and posterior constrictions; with dense goldish ventral and ventro-lateral pubescence, protruding to anterior and posterior pronotal margins; anterior goldish pronotal stripe very narrow, posterior stripe a little wider with central projection at middle; pronotum regularly convex with very dense conjugated punctation.

Scutellum subquadrate with hardly pronounced yellow pubescence.

Elytra strongly long and very narrow, about 4.5 times longer than basal width, a little narrowed near middle, slightly emarginated apically; with distinct outer apical spines and small internal apical angles; elytral design similar to *C. lautus* with central orange area crossed by two black apical bars, black sutural stripe, black lateral borders interrupted near middle and black marginal lines; anterior elytral half with yellow line along curved elytral margin between humeral and marginal elytral lines; elytral carinae disappearing near middle; coarse elytral punctation becomes smaller apically, partly arranged in regular longitudinal rows.

Legs very long, femora strongly clavate, posterior femora nearly reaching elytral apices; 1st joint of posterior tarsi about as long as all others combined.

Abdomen with dense goldish pubescence totally covering 1st and 5th visible segments, and posterior halves of 2nd - 4th segments; posterior margins of last abdominal segments rounded.

Body length: 13.0 mm, width: 2.2 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is similar to *C. lautus* Holzschuh, 1991 because of about same elytral and pronotal design, but strongly differs by long and narrow body with very long legs.

Materials. Holotype, female, Myanmar (N Burma), 50 km E Putao, environs Nan Thi vill., 950 m, 11-16.5.1998, S. Murzin & V. Sinyayev leg. – collection of Maxim Lazarev (Moscow, Russia).

Dere tatianae sp. nov.

(Fig. 2)

Type locality. NW Thailand, Mae Hong Son province, Suen Pu.

Description. A single female available; head, antennae, body and legs black; prothorax red, elytrae dark-blue; frons about as long as wide, with very dense small irregular punctation; genae about as wide as the base of the 1st antennal joint.

Antennae reaching the level of hind margin of 2nd abdominal sternite, strongly thickened apically; 3rd - 10th antennal joints with short apical spines; 1st antennal joint about as wide as 4th joint; 3rd joint about 1.7 times longer; 2nd joint elongated, about 1.5 times longer than wide.

Prothorax about 1.2 times longer than middle width; anteriorly narrower than posteriorly; ventrally and laterally with fine dense silver pubescence; with evenly rounded lateral sides; pronotum strongly convex with shallow central depression; anterior and posterior pronotal margins narrowly diffusely darkened; scutellum black, transverse, glabrous.

Elytra glabrous, about 2.6 times longer than basal width, broadened apically; elytral apices with short external and internal spines; elytral punctuation very dens, all dots conjugating.

Lateral thoracic sides with very dense fine silver pubescence, as well as abdominal sternites.

All femora clavate; posterior margins of the last abdominal segment rounded.

Body length: 8.5 mm; maximal body width (at posterior elytra third): 2.2 mm, body width at elytral bases: 2.1 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is close to *D. punctifrons* Holzschuh 1991, which was also described from Thailand, but elytral apices without long spines and 3rd antennal joint much longer.

Materials. Holotype, female, NW Thailand, Mae Hong Son, Suen Pu, 5.5.1992, Stmed Jen leg. – collection of Maxim Lazarev (Moscow, Russia).

Etymology. Sergey Murzin dedicates the new species to his beloved wife Tatiana, who often followed him in long and dangerous collecting trips to rather distant localities of different continents.

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Figure 1. *Cleomenes putaoensis* sp. nov., holotype, female, dorsal view.

Figure 2. *Dere tatianae* sp. nov., holotype, female, dorsal view.